

LEARNING ENGLISH THROUGH MODERN TECHNOLOGY

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Annotation. This article is devoted to learning English through modern technology. It includes usage of modern technology in learning language and its main features with some examples.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola zamonaviy texnologiyalar orqali ingliz tilini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan va tilni o'rganishda zamonaviy texnologiyalardan foydalanish va uning asosiy xususiyatlarini ba'zi misollar bilan keltirilgan.

Аннотация. Эта статья посвящена изучению английского языка с помощью современных технологий. Она включает в себя использование современных технологий в изучении языка и их основные особенности с некоторыми примерами.

Key words: Foreign Languages, modern technology computer, teaching, SD player, CD player.

The coming of modern technology and the studies that proved the benefits of modern technology bringing to education suggest us using modern technology in English education to achieve a more effective way of English teaching and learning.

In today's sharply developing age science and technology are growing rapidly a new stage and a new era have begun in the teaching of foreign languages in our country In the course of foreign language lessons it is required to use advanced pedagogical technologies interactive media. Textbooks have been created for good foreign language teaching in our republic. In accordance with these requirements. Stands were equipped with new information communication techniques.

This article aims to highlight the role of using modern technology in teaching English as a second language. Discusses different approaches and techniques that can help English language learners improve their learning skills using technology. These techniques include online English language learning websites, computer-aided language learning programs, presentation software,

electronic dictionaries, instant messaging and e-mail programs, listening to CD players, and video clips for learning.

A case study was conducted to appreciate the response of typical English language learners to the use of technology in the learning process. After this practical study, the paper diagnoses the disadvantages and limitations of current conventional English language learning tools and concludes with some suggestions and recommendations. The introduction of information and communication technologies (ICT) into education is creating new learning paradigms. We live in a world reduced to a global village by technology and technological breakthrough supports pedagogical submissions. It may therefore become necessary to rethink how the limitations of second language users can be alleviated through the application of modern technologies. Interactions between new technologies and pedagogical inputs have been found to meet the heterogeneous needs of second language learners to some extent, and any global breakthrough aimed at minimizing learner limitations is a welcome development in a rapidly changing techno In the past, learning and teaching simply meant face-to-face lectures, reading books or printed handouts, taking notes, and completing assignments, usually in the form of answering questions or writing essays. In brief; education, learning and teaching were considered impossible without a teacher, books and chalkboards. Today, education and training have taken on a whole new meaning. Computers are an essential part of any classroom, and teachers use DVDs, CD-ROMs, and videos to show students how things work and work. Students can interact with the subject matter through the use of such web-based tools and CD-ROMs. In addition, each student can progress at his/her own pace. Technology Enables Remote Learning: Perhaps the biggest impact of technology on learning is its ability to help multiple people learn from different places at the same time. Students do not need to meet at a set time or place to learn and receive instruction and information. All you need is a computer connected to a modem (or with a CD drive); these tools can literally provide a classroom” in people’s homes and offices logical world.

With the advancement of technology and the emergence of the digital revolution, language teachers must think of new effective ways to create better language teaching and learning environments supported by multimedia technology. As a result, computer-assisted language learning (CALL) is becoming increasingly popular in language education. Based on the analysis of CALL features, this paper focuses on how multimedia can play an important role in

EFL classrooms. A literature search was conducted on the definition and development of multimedia. In addition, research has been conducted on multimedia literature as a learning method from theoretical and pedagogical aspects. Analyzing the strengths and weaknesses of CALL, some practical and effective teaching methods are discussed that provide professional educators and qualified teachers how to use multimedia effectively in the classroom .

After reviewing the literature, we come to the following conclusion: multimedia English teaching is the latest method with strengths and weaknesses. Considered as the most important factor in teaching effectiveness, teachers should make full use of multimedia tools to create an authentic language teaching and learning environment where students can easily learn the language in a natural and effective way. Multimedia is a term that has recently become widely used in computing. In general, multimedia is a combination of text, sound, images, animation and video. A typical installation includes a CD-ROM drive, a CD-ROM drive, audio hardware, and special hardware capable of displaying advanced graphics. The rapid development of the Internet, which has become a powerful medium, provides a wide range of services, including e-mail, the World Wide Web (WWW), newsgroups, audio and video conferencing, file transfer and exchange, and many businesses. service. It is offered through a special program.” In an educational context, multimedia is text, images, animations, audio, etc. used to retrieve, retrieve, select, link and use information to meet one's needs. It can be described as an integrated environment composed of various media objects.

The advantages of teaching based on modern technologies are many. As time progresses, all things develop according to teaching based on new technologies gives more effective results than teaching language in the way. Interesting lessons through various games increase the student's interest in education and make it easier for kids to learn the language Now days, you can learn a language online even at home. There are many groups of language teaching channels on social networks. You can easily access it via computer or phone. This is also an opportunity for students.

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